

$E = mc^2$: Mass-Energy Equivalence

Chinnaraji Annamalai
School of Management, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, India
Email: anna@iitkgp.ac.in
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0992-2584>

Abstract: This paper proves that $E = mc^2$ or mass-energy equation in a simple way.

Keywords: electromagnetic wave, momentum, quantum

1. Introduction

Electromagnetic waves are formed when an electric field couples with a magnetic field that differ from mechanical waves in that they do not require a medium to propagate. This means that electromagnetic waves [1] can travel not only through air and solid materials, but also through the vacuum of space. We know that all the waves carry energy. Thus, the electromagnetic wave carries energy. A quantum is the smallest unit of a phenomenon. For examples, a quantum of light is a photon, and a quantum of electricity is an electron. These are basic information which is used to prove that $E = mc^2$, where E, m , and c denote energy, mass, and speed of light respectively.

2. Mass-Energy Equation

The momentum (P) of an electromagnetic wave is the energy (E) carried by the electromagnetic wave divided by the speed of light (c).

$$P = \frac{E}{c} \Rightarrow E = Pc. \quad (1)$$

In another way, momentum (P) is defined as the product of mass (m) and velocity (v) of an object.

$$P = mv. \quad (2)$$

Let's consider the speed of light as the velocity of light ($c = v$)

$$\text{Then, } P = mc. \quad (3)$$

From the equations (1) and (2), we obtain

$$E = Pc \Rightarrow E = (mc) \times c \Rightarrow E = mc^2.$$

Hence, mass-energy equation is proved.

3. Conclusion

In this article, $E = mc^2$ or mass-energy equation is proved in a simple way.

References

- [1] National Aeronautics and Space Administration, Science Mission Directorate. (2010). Anatomy of an Electromagnetic Wave. http://science.nasa.gov/ems/02_anatomy.